

AGRO4AGRI

D8.2 Website of the project

Sofia Oliveira, FI Group

Version V1.0

31/10/2024

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

AGRO4AGRI's details

Project name	FOSTERING THE ADVANCED USE OF AGROCHEMICALS FOR A SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE
Project acronym	AGRO4AGRI
Grant Agreement number	101130890
Duration and dates	48 months (1 May 2024 – 30 April 2028)
Call and topic	HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-34: Advanced (nano and bio-based) materials for Sustainable Agriculture
Granting authority	European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA), under the powers delegated by the European Commission
Official project website	agro4agri.eu

The AGRO4AGRI consortium

N°	NAME	ROLE	COUNTRY
1	AINIA (AINIA)	Coordinator	Spain
2	FUNDACION CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DE COMPONENTES (CTC)	Beneficiary	Spain
3	SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET (SDU)	Beneficiary	Denmark
4	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET (DTU)	Beneficiary	Denmark
5	FUNDACION GRUPO CAJAMAR (FGC)	Beneficiary	Spain
6	PROEFCENTRUM HOOGSTRATEN (PCH)	Beneficiary	Belgium
7	F. INICIATIVAS, CONSULTADORA E GESTAO, UNIPessoal, LDA (FIG)	Beneficiary	Portugal
7.1	F. INICIATIVAS ESPANA I MAS D MAS I SLU (FI GROUP)	Affiliated Entity	Spain
8	SIPCAM OXON SPA (SIPCAM)	Beneficiary	Italy
9	INSTITUT FUR HOHERE STUDIEN - INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES (HIS)	Beneficiary	Austria
10	SYSPRO AUTOMATION SL (SYSPRO)	Beneficiary	Spain
11	MIRAT FERTILIZANTES SL (MIRAT)	Beneficiary	Spain

N°	NAME	ROLE	COUNTRY
12	OPTIMAT LIMITED (OPTIMAT)	Associated partner	United Kingdom

Project's summary

Agrochemicals are chemical products used in agriculture such as fertilizers, plant-biostimulants or pesticides. The application of fertilizers in synergistic combination with biostimulants provides the nutrients required for enhancing the crops yield, while pesticides are used to reduce the risk of loss from plant diseases and weeds on agricultural production. Today, the agricultural sector faces several challenges, namely the loss and leaching of fertilisers, the large amounts of pesticides used, the bioaccumulation and bioconcentration of them and the high dependency on water availability.

In this context, nano and biotechnology strategies have recently gained more interest in the agricultural sector compared to conventional agricultural techniques.

AGRO4AGRI seeks to provide ground-breaking and Safe and Sustainable by Design solutions for plant nutrition and protection consisting of nano and biobased controlled delivery fertilisers and plant biostimulants, and target-specific biopesticides based on RNAi technology, both for enhanced agrochemicals use efficiency. AGRO4AGRI involves R&D and validation stages, aiming to minimize in the long term the use of agrochemicals in agriculture in more than 50% to be aligned with the Farm to Fork Strategy, among other EU initiatives. Further project developments include the evaluation of safety, social and economic impacts, activities to promote society and policy makers engagement to bring wider impacts and better fulfil EU targets and position Europe at the forefront of the agroindustry.

Document details

Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Deliverable n°	D8.2
Deliverable title	Website of the project
Lead beneficiary	7 - FIG
Work package and task	WP8, T8.2
Document version	V1.0
Contractual delivery date	M6 (31/10/2024)
Actual delivery date	31/10/2024
Dissemination Level	Public
Purpose	The main aim of this document is to provide a short overview of the AGRO4AGRI project website, developed under the Work Package 8. This public website serves to present the project's objectives, work packages and consortium, as well as to disseminate project related events, activities, results and any project documents or materials. It is also the central communication channel, linking to its social networks,

newsletter, etc. This document describes the scope, and structure of the project website, and explains its development process.

Document's abstract

This deliverable outlines the strategic development and implementation of the AGRO4AGRI project website. The website serves as a centralised platform, providing stakeholders with a user-friendly interface to access to the project updates, resources, and interactive tools. The website design prioritises inclusivity, ensuring compliance with web accessibility standards to accommodate user needs. Through meticulous planning and execution, this deliverable contributes to the overall success of the AGRO4AGRI project by establishing a digital hub not only to disseminates information effectively but also fosters a sense of community and engagement among the stakeholders.

Document's revision history

The following table describes the main changes done in the document since it was created.

REVISION	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR (PARTNER)
V.0.1	23/10/2024	First draft	Sofia Oliveira (FI Group)
V.0.2	30/10/2024	Second draft including consortium feedback	All partners
V.1.0	31/10/2024	Final version to be submitted, incorporating feedback from the AGRO4AGRI consortium	Sofia Oliveira (FI Group)

Terminology and acronyms

TERM/ACRONYM	EXPLANATION
ASAR	Active substance adsorption ratio
BRL	Business Readiness Level
dsRNA	Double-stranded RNA
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment

MSN	Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticle
NC	Nanocellulose derivative
NCH	Nanocellulose hydrogel
NCL	Nanoclay
NF	Nanocellulose foam
NFC	Nanofiber of cellulose
ORE	Open Research Europe
PB	Plant Biostimulant
PPP	Plant Protection Products
RNAi	RNA interference
SAP	Super Absorbing Polymer
SEIA	Social, economic and sustainability impact assessment
SO	Specific objective
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
USP	Unique Selling Proposition

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2. INTRODUCTION TO THE PROJECT'S WEBSITE

2.1. Scope

This document showcases the deliverable **D8.2 Website of the project**, which belongs to task **T8.2 Dissemination activities, communication and marketing materials**, framed within the work package **WP8 Dissemination, communication and exploitation** of the AGRO4AGRI project.

The **objective of WP8** is to maximise the impact of the European Commission funded project beyond its consortium and time frame, raising awareness among the different target audiences and stakeholders that may use this project as a starting point for new developments, thus leading to a virtuous circle of research and innovation.

As such, this work package is responsible for the dissemination of project progress and results to scientific and industrial audiences and developing exploitation strategies for any relevant technologies and concepts produced throughout the project. Moreover, it will contribute to common communication and dissemination activities with similar European projects and/or initiatives supported actions.

Among all these communication and dissemination activities of the project, the website will serve as the central online communication channel, allowing the consortium to **deliver information** on the project's progress and make **developments available** to the public in an easy and agile manner. It will describe project's scope, work packages, and consortium, and will be periodically updated with the latest project activities, events, results, and publications. Moreover, the promotional materials, public deliverables, and open-access scientific publications will be available on it (D8.1).

Thus, the website will constitute **an important source**, if not the main, of information for the scientific community, industrial audiences, and policymakers, who will benefit from the reports and research publications made available in the project's website. The media will also find on it a reliable source of information for their research and articles. What is more, the general audience will have the chance to discover the project's scope and expected results in an accessible manner.

The AGRO4AGRI website will also link **to other online communication channels** of the project, especially its social media profiles and newsletter, including a form for users to subscribe to the official newsletter and AGRO4AGRI's stakeholder database.

The website has been created at the beginning of the project and will be active for six years, including two years after the project's ending, to facilitate the exploitation of its results. The design is aligned with the project's brandbook (available in [ANNEX 1. BERTHA's brandbook](#)) and is meant to be visually attractive and easily navigated through.

The AGRO4AGRI project website is available at: agro4agri.eu.

2.2. Main contents

First, the website presents **general information** on the project, such as its scope, work packages and consortium members. This content is available on its homepage and is meant to be static, although some specific modifications or updates can be made over the course of the project. It is presented in a written format, together with some visuals that make it more appealing to users.

During the whole project, the website will be frequently fed with **news** on any project updates, activities, **events**, or results, as well as in-depth content on specific topics related to its tasks or field of research. These will be published through web posts, in a blog format, which will also contribute to improving the Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) of the whole website.

The website will also host the **project's public resources**, in the form of downloadable documents or by directing to an external link, most of them in PDF format. These may include the project's branding and promotional materials (brochure, infographics), newsletters and press releases, public project deliverables, and scientific and professional publications.

Finally, the website links to **other online communication channels** of the project, encouraging users to visit them. These include the project's social networks, subscription to its newsletter, and contact form. In the same way, those communication channels will link to the project's website, allowing a transfer of traffic from users and thus increasing the website visits.

2.3. Development process

The first task involved the establishment of the website's scope, target audience, objectives, tree structure and main contents, considering all the guidelines provided in the Grant Agreement for this deliverable D8.2 Website of the project, as well as for deliverable **D8.1 First Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication activities**.

Having this strategy clear, the domain "www.agro4agri.eu" was chosen and a hosting was purchased that fulfils all the requirements in terms of available space, functionality, security, and privacy, among others. To ensure security and avoid any potential cyberattacks, an SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) Certificate has been installed and the anti-DDoS (Distributed Denial-of-Service) technology has been implemented on the website. A WordPress account was also purchased to facilitate content management, together with an email account to centralise the project's messages.

Moreover, **different accounts** were created to set up other online communication channels of the project, and thus, be able to link them on the website. This includes a Google account to manage the Google Analytics and Google Search Engine tools, a MailChimp account for the project newsletters, and the additional development profiles on LinkedIn, Twitter/X, and YouTube to serve as the project's social media channels.

A **website developer** was contracted to create and implement de website's architecture and design, and to build it in the real hosting and domain, using WordPress as the Content Management System (CMS). Several interactions, revisions and corrections followed to reach the current version of the website, with an appealing design, a good structure, easy navigation and all the required initial contents.

The **design** was created considering the previously developed visual identity for the project, including its logotype, brandbook, typography, colours, and suitable images, among other elements. Moreover, the design was thought to be visually appealing and offer an intuitive and accessible way to navigate through the different contents, following the standard recommendations for a good User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI), and being mobile-responsive. The website structure and content can ben found on [ANNEX 2. Website structure and content](#).

Finally, all the initial contents were **published and tested, both by FI Group and the remaining consortium**, to ensure their proper functionality, fixing any issues that might have arisen during the process. After their final validation, the website was made **publicly available** online at: agro4agri.eu.

Throughout the project's lifetime, the website will be **frequently updated** and fed with new contents, and it will also remain available for four years after its ending to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

3. CONFIGURATION, OPTIMISATION AND RESULTS

3.1. Technologies, tools and security

The dominium agro4agri.eu has been purchased to host the project's website for a period of six years, including the four years of project duration and an additional two years to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

A trust-worthy **hosting** supplier has been chosen, that also counts on enough space to host the website and all its contents, both in the present and future years of the project.

The website also counts on an **SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) Certificate** that verifies the website's identity and allows an encrypted connection between servers and browsers, thus ensuring the security and privacy protection of any user that visits the website and preventing hackers to modifying or reading private information. Moreover, the **anti-DDoS (Distributed Denial-of-Service) technology** has been implemented to filter potential threats in the website traffic through connection tracking, IP reputation lists, deep packet inspection, blacklisting or rate limiting.

The website has been built using **WordPress**, a popular and standard Content Management System (CMS) that offers flexibility and accessibility to modify any element of the website content or design, in an easy way at any time. It also allows to publish new posts and any type of content on the website over the course of the project, without having any technical knowledge of web programming.

Moreover, an **official email account** has been created with the same domain, "info@agro4agri.eu".

For the sake of analysing the performance of the website and studying its Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), it has been connected to **Google Analytics** and **Google Search Console**. These free tools offer valuable data on the website's traffic (visits, users, sources, locations...) and on its performance on the Google Search Engine.

Finally, the website includes a subscription form for the project newsletter that is connected to MailChimp, a popular and standard email marketing tool that allows to manage the list of subscribers, design email templates, and create and distribute newsletters, among other functionalities.

3.2. Search Engine and Optimisation (SEO)

The website has been configured to maximise its **organic positioning** in search engines.

SEO optimisation is a work in progress that will last for the whole duration of the website and whose results will show over time, supported by a good **content strategy** and an effective strategy for **off-page SEO**.

3.3. Legal compliance and data protection

AGRO4AGRI's website complies with all legal requirements present on the **European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**.

In the **subscription form for the newsletter**, the user voluntarily provides his/her first name and email account to receive email communications of the project. By submitting the form, the user accepts the following statement:

I have read and accept this website's Terms of Use and Privacy Policy. By submitting this form, I hereby declare accepting that my personal data are collected and processed for receiving communications about the AGRO4AGRI project.

This data will be processed by FI Group through the MailChimp email marketing software, a standard tool for digital marketing. The contacts will only be used with the purpose of sending email communications about the project, specifically the email newsletters foreseen in its communication plan. Moreover, these contacts will be

erased after the project has ended, or sooner in case the user wants to voluntarily be erased from the subscription list.

The website also includes a **contact form**, where the user voluntarily provides his/her name and surname, organisation, and email address, for the purpose of sending a message directly to the project's team. This message will be received on the official project email "info@agro4agri.eu", managed by FI Group. This data will be used to contact back the message sender, and he/she will be also included in the email communications of the project, since the user has accepted the same statement present in the newsletter subscription form when submitting the message. The same considerations on data protection will be applied to both forms.

On the other hand, the tool used to analyse the traffic to the website, **Google Analytics**, complies with this policy and does not collect any personal data from users that may identify them as individuals. On the contrary, it merely provides aggregated, statistic data about the main sources and locations of visits, among other items, by using website cookies.

All other matters regarding the website's legal compliance, privacy, or security can be found at the bottom of the website, in the links to access the webpages **Terms of use, Privacy policy and Cookies policy**.

3.4. Content strategy and analysis of results

An effective content strategy will be developed considering all the communication channels of the project, including the project's website, which will be frequently fed with new contents on the project's general information, activities, results, publications, etc.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, at least **1,000 visits** will be achieved on the website per year. Traffic will grow over time thanks to the following strategies:

- Frequent updates and **new content** published on the website.
- Strategies of **Search Engine Optimisation (SEO)** to maximise its positioning in search engines, especially Google Search.
- Linking to the website from **other project communication channels**, mainly the project's LinkedIn and Twitter/X posts, email newsletters, and promotional materials.

To analyse these results, data will be used from the **Google Analytics tool**. Other elements and indicators will also be analysed to maximise the website's performance, such as:

- Number of users and new users visiting the website.
- Source and location of visits.
- Time spent, engagement rate, and bounce rate.
- User's journey and best performing webpages and web posts.

4. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. AGRO4AGRI's brandbook

AGRO4AGRI IDENTITY & LOGO

AGRO4AGRI identity purposes:

- Define and standardise AGRO4AGRI's project image
- Develop a manual of rules and standards to achieve a cohesive and uniform AGRO4AGRI signature and visual identity

FULL COLOUR

HORIZONTAL

POSITIVE

main version

NEGATIVE

VERTICAL

POSITIVE

NEGATIVE

AGRO4AGRI IDENTITY & LOGO

MONOCHROME

HORIZONTAL

VERTICAL

3

AGRO4AGRI LOGO & STANDARD RULES

The AGRO4AGRI project's logo **must be prominently displayed** in all documents, materials and equipment produced by the project, as a **requirement for EU funding**. This includes its presence in events that the project organises or participates in.

Use preferably the main version of the logo: **horizontal and positive**.

Use the alternative vertical and positive version if it offers a better display.

Choose the negative version when strictly necessary. For example, if:

- The printing material only allows one single colour (**see slide 5**).
- The logo must have a transparent background (for example, over a photograph – **see slide 5**).
- The logo is placed in a design with a different (and unmatching) visual identity.

Do not modify the logo and respect the bounded free space around it.

For printing purposes, the logo must not be reduced by less than 5 cm in width in the horizontal version and by 3 cm in the vertical version.

Always write the **project's acronym** in capital letters: AGRO4AGRI.

4

AGRO4AGRI LOGO & COLOURED BACKGROUNDS

AGRO4AGRI COLOURS

AGRO4AGRI colour palette:

- The colour palette is an important element of AGRO4AGRI's visual identity and must therefore be reproduced as accurately as possible.
- Depending on the type of media to be printed, the **main colours in this manual must always be respected**.

COLOUR 1
 C70M 42Y100K 38
 RGB 729132
 HTML #485c20
 PANTONE P 159-16 C

COLOUR 2
 C48M 17Y100K 3
 RGB 1521703
 HTML #98aa03
 PANTONE 375 C

COLOUR 3
 C23M 0Y70K 0
 RGB 214223104HTML
 #66d168 PANTONE P
 160-8 C

COLOUR 4
 C1M 7Y10K 0
 RGB 253242 233
 HTML #d12e9
 PANTONE P 541 C

AGRO4AGRI TYPOGRAPHY

AGRO4AGRI typography:

- Typography is an essential element that characterizes identity.
- To standardise internal and external communication pieces, the **DIN standard font** was determined to produce materials and documents in all available typographic weights for a greater degree of typographic hierarchy.

	main typography DIN
REGULAR	ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklm nopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890
BOLD	ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklm nopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890
ITALIC	<i>ABCDEFGHIJKLM NOPQRSTUVWXYZ</i> <i>abcdefghijklm nopqrstuvwxyz</i> <i>1234567890</i>

The font size and colour must be adapted to the context, using exclusively the **brand colours** and **black/white**.

7

ACKNOWLEDGING EU FUNDING

The **EU emblem** is the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding. No other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support.

All communication activities related to the project (including media relations, conferences, seminars and information material such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc. in electronic form via traditional or social media), as well as **any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result** funded by the grant, must acknowledge EU support and display the **European flag (emblem)** and **funding statement** (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

The emblem must be in '**prominent display**', at least **1 cm high** and the **bounded free space** around it must be respected. It shall **not be modified or merged** with any other graphic element.

The logo is the brand's most distinctive element in all its communication actions. Whenever possible, **it should appear on a white background with the main color**. When this is not possible, the following transformation must be respected for application on a coloured background.

8

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ACKNOWLEDGING EU FUNDING

The following disclaimer must also be included in any public document or material of the project (such as publications, website, brochures, videos, equipment...):

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This disclaimer must appear next to the EU emblem and funding statement, written in a standard, easy-to-read font, **preferably “Arial”**.

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More information at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information/sources/logo-download-center_en

COMBINING DIFFERENT LOGOS

It is not necessary to include all partners' logos in every project document or material. It is only mandatory to include the project's logo, together with the EU emblem and funding statement, as stated previously. Nevertheless, it is recommended that the partners' logos are present in relevant materials (the project's website, brochure, etc.)

AGRO4AGRI

PARTNER 1 PARTNER 4 PARTNER 7 PARTNER 10 PARTNER 13
PARTNER 2 PARTNER 5 PARTNER 8 PARTNER 11
PARTNER 3 PARTNER 6 PARTNER 9 PARTNER 12

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In case you need to include the logos of all partners that take part in the project, they must be smaller in size than the project's logo, following this example

The EU emblem must be displayed at least the same size as the biggest logo

If the project's logo is to be displayed together with the logo of another organisation or project, they must be both in the same size.

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AGRO4AGRI

BRANDBOOK
version 1.1
24th September 2024

**Thank you for
your commitment**

For more information, please contact:

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EU communication consultant

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ANNEX 2. Website structure and content

Header

Footer

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Made by **LWM**

Homepage

Top banner

Horizon Europe project meant to revolutionize plant nutrition and protection

Through cutting-edge nano and biotechnology demonstrating sustainable agrochemical solutions for deliver innovative solutions under the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework

[About](#)

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About AGRO4AGRI

About the AGRO4AGRI Project

AGRO4AGRI is an EU-funded project set to revolutionize plant nutrition and protection through cutting-edge nano and biotechnology. Within 4 years, by enhancing fertilizer efficiency and developing species-specific nematicides, the project aims to deliver sustainable and innovative solutions under the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework.

Funded with €5.3 million from the Horizon Europe Programme, AGRO4AGRI brings together a diverse consortium of 12 high-profile European and non-European partners, including academic centres, research organizations, SMEs, foundations, and large companies from 7 countries. The project focuses on implementing nano and biobased controlled delivery systems for fertilizers, combined with plant biostimulants, to boost nutrient use efficiency. Additionally, it aims to develop target-specific biopesticides using RNAi technology, which are safe for humans and non-target organisms.

AGRO4AGRI's solutions are designed to be biodegradable and environmentally friendly, reducing the need for traditional agrochemicals. Aligned with the European Green Deal, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, AGRO4AGRI aims to cut nutrient and pesticide use in agriculture by over 40% and 50%, respectively.

The project seeks to address soil contamination, reduce water consumption, improve agrochemical efficiency, and minimize water pollution. By promoting sustainable food systems and commercializing innovative solutions, AGRO4AGRI aims to strengthen the EU's leadership in the sustainable agri-food sector and enhance its industrial competitiveness on a global scale.

Work Packages

Our Work Packages

<p>1</p> <p>Project management & coordination</p> <p>AINIA will monitor the correct implementation of the project, task & milestone completion and submission...</p>	<p>2</p> <p>Process and solutions design according to SSbD principles</p> <p>The purpose of this work package is to ensure that process and solutions developed in the project are aligned...</p>	<p>3</p> <p>Development of advanced delivery systems for fertilizers</p> <p>The objective of this WP is to develop and characterise inorganic and biobased nanocarriers which will be...</p>	<p>4</p> <p>Development of novel safe and sustainable target-specific nematicides</p> <p>RNAi technology will be employed to silence vital genes of one of the most elusive nematode plagues, the root...</p>
<p>5</p> <p>Integration and upscale formulation of delivery systems and advanced agrochemical...</p> <p>Scale up the production of delivery systems. Develop controlled delivery fertilizer formulas. Develop Plant...</p>	<p>6</p> <p>Pilot demonstration of AGRO4AGRI solutions</p> <p>Pilot demonstration of AGRO4AGRI solution through field trials.</p>	<p>7</p> <p>Environmental, socio-economic and sustainability assessment</p> <p>The objectives for WP7 include conducting a comprehensive hazard assessment of the chemicals and...</p>	<p>8</p> <p>Dissemination, communication and exploitation</p> <p>The WP8 aims to strategically plan and execute activities to ensure the successful dissemination...</p>

Consortium

The AGRO4AGRI Project Consortium

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News

Latest News & Articles

Article

The Kick-off to revolutionize plant nutrition and protection

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